

Scientific study in experimental facilities to evaluate the impacts of covered veranda on the welfare of broiler chickens on farm

Scientific study in experimental facilities to evaluate the impacts of covered veranda on the welfare of broiler chickens on farm

Frédérique Mocz¹ and Maryse Guinebretière¹

¹*Epidemiology, Health and Welfare Unit, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), Ploufragan, France*

December 2024

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Anja B. Riber for her review. This project, carried out in the framework of the UMTs BIRD and SANIVOL, was made possible by the financial support provided by the French special account for agricultural and rural development, CASDAR (project **no. 20AIP1619988 COCORICO**).

Disclaimer

This report is a publication of the European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare for Poultry and small farmed animals. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA was designated by the European Union on 4 October 2019 through Regulation (EU) 2019/1685, in accordance with Articles 95 and 96 of Regulation (EU) 2017/625. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This report can be downloaded for free at [10.5281/zenodo.14512668](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512668)

Citation : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512668>

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA produces its reports according to internationally accepted scientific standards. However, it cannot accept liability for any damage resulting from the use of the results of this study or the application of the advice contained in it.

 info@eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu

 <https://www.eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contents

1	Executive Summary (1/2 page)	4
2	Introduction	5
3	Material and Methods	6
	Data collection	6
	Body weight and mortality	6
	Leg health and gait score	6
	Litter Quality	7
	Activity level	8
	Covered veranda use	9
	Statistical analysis	9
4	Results	10
	Body weight and mortality	10
	Leg health and gait score	11
	Litter quality, water and feed consumption	11
	Activity level	11
	Covered veranda use	13
5	Discussion	15
6	Conclusions	17
7	References	18
8	Annex 1	20

1 Executive Summary (1/2 page)

In standard broiler production systems, birds lack outdoor access and spend their entire lives in the same barren environment. A covered veranda can provide improved living conditions for broilers while protecting them from predators and disease risks. This study aimed to evaluate the welfare and health of broilers with access to a covered veranda. Redbro broilers were randomly assigned to six identical rooms, each containing 2,478 birds. Half of the rooms had covered veranda access from 22 days of age (D22), while the other half had no such access (control). Several animal-based indicators were assessed, including leg health and gait (D36), activity levels (D34 and D37), use of the covered veranda (from D22 to slaughter), mortality (all rearing period), and body weight (of the whole group automatically during all the rearing period and, of 150 broilers per treatment manually at D8, D11, D22, D29 and D36). Litter quality (D34 and D37), as well as feed and water consumption (all rearing period), were also monitored. Covered veranda access did not affect mortality, body weight, litter quality, or feed and water consumption. None of the broilers from either treatment exhibited gait issues or footpad dermatitis. However, the prevalence of hock burns was lower in the broilers having access to a covered veranda. Additionally, more active behaviours were observed with chickens from the covered veranda treatment than from the control treatment. The covered verandas were well-used, with usage increasing as the broilers aged. Within day, a high use was observed in the morning where after it decreased. Providing access to a covered veranda improved bird welfare without negatively impacting zootechnical indicators.

2 Introduction

In standard broiler productions, the birds do not have outdoor access and spend all their life in the same environment. The general lack of environmental enrichment in conventional barns may cause broiler chickens to experience difficulties in expressing their natural behaviours such as foraging, perching, dustbathing, exploring or even sunbathing (EFSA, 2023). While the outdoor range access can fulfil the behavioural needs of broilers and possibly improve their welfare (El-Deek and El-Sabrou, 2019), it may also lead to some challenges, for instance predator attacks or disease risks such as avian influenza. A covered veranda can bring some of the advantages of the outdoor range for the birds while protecting them from predators and disease risks. A covered veranda is defined as a non-heated area adjacent to the barn, accessible to the birds via popholes in the side of the barn and partially exposed to the outdoor environmental conditions (EFSA, 2023). It has a roof, is separated from outdoor by wire mesh and, possibly windbreaks, and the floor is covered with litter. Besides providing birds the conditions to express natural behaviours, the covered veranda gives birds extra space (although only if its surface is not included in the stocking density calculation) and a choice to access daylight and outdoor conditions (e.g. fresh air, different temperatures). This choice may positively impact broiler welfare, as making choices enables them to exercise control, thereby increasing their motivation, performance, and wellbeing (Englund and Cronin, 2023).

Although some previous studies examining different rearing systems included outdoor access with a covered veranda (Dawkins et al., 2003, Bergmann et al., 2016, Gocsik et al., 2016, Bergmann et al., 2017, Louton et al., 2019, Goransson et al., 2021), no studies have investigated the impact of covered verandas *per se* on the welfare of broiler chickens. In the present study, the aim was to assess the activity and the use of the covered veranda by Redbro broilers, considered a fast-growing strain, although slower growing than Ross 308 broiler chickens. For the evaluation of the impact of the covered veranda on the health and welfare of the broilers, the focus was on animal-based measures and on zootechnical indicators.

3 Material and Methods

A total of 14,872 one-day-old Redbro broilers (from 31-week-old breeders) was delivered in March 2023 and split randomly into six identical 162 m² rooms of the ANSES Avian experimental building (Ploufragan, France). In each room, 2,478 chicks were placed to reach a final density of 26 kg/m² when slaughtered at 1.9 kg and 38 days of age. All the rooms had natural light access provided by eight windows (90 cm × 30 cm) from 08:00 to 19:00. The natural light was completed, when needed, by artificial light guaranteeing 30 lux during 18 h per day from 6 days of age (from 06:00 to 23:59). In each room, all birds had access to two hanging round scales (8 cm high, 60 cm diameter), one elevated platform of 2 m² with access ramps of 1 m² from both sides (4 m² of platform in total) and three alfalfa bales (each 20 kg, 30 cm high, 50 cm long, 30 cm wide). Sawdust litter was provided to birds in each room following standard management practices (1.2 kg/m²). All chickens had permanent ad libitum access to the feed and water. Half of the rooms had four 24/24h opened popholes to let broilers access to a 72 m² covered veranda (**CV**) from 22 days of age, whereas the other half of the rooms have closed popholes (**C**). The floor of the covered verandas was concrete, covered with straw pellets, and the side facing the outdoor area was made of wire mesh. The roof was equipped with an anti-drip film to prevent condensation and dripping onto the broilers. Windbreak nets were installed at the level of the wired walls to protect the broilers from the rain and wind. The local temperatures, according to meteorological records, ranged from 1.2°C to 21.1°C during the period when the birds had access to the covered verandas.

Data collection

Body weight and mortality

Every day, hanging round scales (2 per room) automatically registered body weights of broilers positioned on it. A mean body weight was automatically calculated every day for each room. Additionally, 150 randomly selected birds per treatment (50 per room, sex balanced as soon as feasible: from D29) were manually and individually weighed at D8, D15, D22, D29 and D36.

The number of dead broilers per room was recorded daily (found dead and culled if needed to avoid birds suffering).

Leg health and gait score

At D36, the broilers selected for weighing were also assessed for gait score and presence and severity of footpad dermatitis and hock burns (150 broilers per treatment, 50 per room, sex balanced) by the same two trained assessors. Scoring ranged from 0 to 2 points for each criterion,

the lowest score indicating the best condition (Table 1). After weighing, the broiler was carried by a person who presented both legs to the observer. The observer examined both legs and scored the condition of the worst one. Then, the bird was returned to the group, and the second observer recorded the gait score while observing the bird from behind, and gently encouraged it to walk with a stick if needed.

Table 1. Scoring of footpad dermatitis, hock burns and gait score (Guinebretière et al., 2024)

	Score 0	Score 1	Score 2
Footpad dermatitis	None or slight, very superficial lesions, slight discoloration on a limited area, slight hyperkeratosis or scarred skin	Moderate and severe discoloration, superficial lesion, darkened papillae	Severe dermatitis ulcers or scabs of significant size, signs of bleeding or severely swollen foot pads
Hock burns			
Gait score	Normal gait, agile, with or without imbalance	Broiler walks more than 1.50 m but has difficulty in walking; limps	Broiler walks less than 1.50 m, and/or is severely lame, preventing movement

Litter Quality

On D34 and 37, the litter quality of each room was assessed by a single assessor in three areas (in the middle of the room, under drinkers and between feeders) with the Welfare Quality protocol (Welfare Quality®, 2009): score 0= completely dry and flaky, score 1= dry, but not easy to move with foot, score 2= leaves imprint of foot and will form a ball if compacted, but ball does not stay together well, score 3= sticks to boots and sticks readily in ball if compacted, score 4= sticks to boots once the cap or compacted crust is broken.

Activity level

The behaviour of the broilers was recorded at 34 and 37 days of age by a single observer. Following a 1 min acclimation period to the observer's presence, the observations were conducted during 3 min. Every occurrence of birds walking and running (definitions in Table 2, adapted from Lourenco da Silva et al. (2021)) in a 2 m² “empty” area (far from feeders, drinkers and enrichments) inside the rooms, and in the covered verandas of the CV treatment were noted, without individual identification. In addition, the observer counted the total number of broilers included lying birds in the 2 m² observed area before and after each 3 minutes observations periods using scan sampling method.

Due to technical constraints, the number of repetitions per room and covered veranda varied between D34 and D37 (Table 3). The observations took place between 9:20 AM and 3:45 PM and were evenly distributed between the two treatments across both the morning and the afternoon, ensuring that neither treatment was assessed exclusively during a specific time period.

Table 2. Experimental ethogram adapted from (Lourenco da Silva et al., 2021)

Behaviour	Definition
<i>Walking</i>	Broiler moves at a slow pace
<i>Running</i>	Broiler moves at a fast pace and occasionally flaps its wings
<i>Lying/resting</i>	Broiler lies on the litter while the head rests on the ground or is erected; eyes may be open or shut

Table 3. Number of behavioural observation sessions in the rooms of both treatments and covered verandas on D34 and D37.

	D34	D37
Indoor	4 times in each CV and C rooms	3 times in each CV and C rooms
Covered verandas	2 times in each covered verandas	2 times in each covered verandas

Covered veranda use

The use of the covered verandas was evaluated by one single observer through video recordings. The surface videoed was half the size of the covered veranda (36 m² from the popholes to the middle of the covered veranda's length). On video recordings, the number of chickens was counted 7 times every day, using scan sampling, between 22 and 37 days of age at 8:00, 10:00, 12:00, 14:00, 16:00, 18:00, and 20:00 h.

Statistical analysis

Data pre-processing and statistical analyses were analysed using R software v. 4.0.3 and RStudio (R Core Team, 2023). Initially, several statistical models were tested for data analysis, each incorporating different variables as either random or fixed effects. Depending on the data analysed, the final models were selected based on their stability.

After visually validating the distributions of the model residuals for normality, a linear regression model was used to analyse the variance in body weight data (both manually weighed and automatically registered) and the percentage of lying birds. Generalized negative binomial regression models were employed for analysing total mortality data and mortality after D22 (open access to covered verandas). To analyse the variables (broiler age, hour of the day, room) impacting the number of broilers counted in the covered verandas, a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) with a negative binomial distribution was used.

To quantify the activity level, standardized occurrence rates were calculated by dividing the total occurrences of walking and running behaviours observed in 3 min duration by the average number of birds present in the 2 m² observation area during the 3 min of observation (averaging the number of birds counted in the area before and after the 3 min of observation), and then multiplying by 100 to express the rate as occurrences per 100 broilers. In addition, the percentage of broilers in a lying position in the area was noted before and after the 3 min of observation. These standardized occurrence rates for walking and running behaviours, and the percentage of lying birds, were then analysed using linear regression models. In the activity level analysis, behaviours were analysed in three different ways:

- Comparison of behaviours observed inside the CV rooms with those noted inside the C rooms: "CV vs. C, Indoor activity".
- Comparison of behaviours observed in the covered verandas with those observed inside the CV rooms: "Indoor vs. outside, CV treatment".

- Comparison of the two treatments, using the average activity level of the CV group (mean of behaviours noted in the covered verandas and inside the CV rooms) compared to the behaviours of the control group (behaviours noted inside the C rooms): "CV vs. C".

Due to absence of normality of the residuals, the water and feed consumption and the litter quality were analysed with Mann-Whitney non-parametric tests. Chi-square tests for each severity score between treatments were used for data on gait score, footpad dermatitis and hock burns.

For all analyses, when interactions were significant, post-hoc analyses were carried out by post-hoc analysis of estimated marginal means with Tukey adjustment. Differences were considered significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

4 Results

Body weight and mortality

The total mortality was $3.90 \pm 1.37\%$ for CV group (including $3.10 \pm 1.43\%$ in the first 8 days of age) and $7.12 \pm 5.05\%$ for C group (including $6.07 \pm 4.80\%$ in the first 8 days of age), but no significant effect of treatment was found on the total mortality ($p = 0.15$) or specifically after D22 ($p = 0.58$) when covered verandas were accessible.

There was no significant difference between treatments for manually weighed broilers at any age ($p = 0.88$) (Table 4). Similarly, for the data from the weighing scales, there was no effect of treatment on the birds' body weight ($p = 0.47$).

Table 4. Mean weights (g) (\pm standard deviations) of broilers from both treatments, manually weighed at D8, D15, D22, D29, and D36.

	D8	D15	D22	D29	D36
Group C	166.7 (18.7)	414.4 (42.4)	816.3 (79.9)	1270.0 (143.1)	1815.9 (237.4)
Group CV	164.4 (17.0)	408.9 (41.9)	805.1 (73.7)	1269.6 (153.8)	1825.0 (225.1)

Leg health and gait score

All birds scored for gait and footpad dermatitis had the best score (score 0) at D36 in both groups, requiring no statistical analysis. Considering hock burns, no broiler was scored with the worst score (score 2). However, broilers from the C group had more moderate hock lesions (score 1) than broilers from the group CV (15.3% in C group vs. 1.3% in CV group; $p < 0.001$).

Litter quality, water and feed consumption

There was no effect of the treatment on the litter quality at D34 (average CV score: 0.67 ± 1 ; average C score: 0.33 ± 0.71 ; $p=0.53$) or D37 (average CV score: 0.67 ± 1 ; average C score: 0.56 ± 0.73 ; $p=1$).

There was no impact of covered veranda access on the feed or water consumption (Table 5).

Table 5. Mean feed and water consumption per bird (\pm standard deviation) for both treatments during the total rearing period

	Group C	Group CV	Significance of effect (p)
Final mean feed consumption per bird (Kg)	3.04 (0.06)	3.05 (0.04)	0.50
Final mean water consumption per bird (L)	5.63 (0.02)	5.57 (0.07)	0.88

Activity level

“Indoor vs. outside, CV treatment”: More walking and running behaviours were observed in the covered verandas than inside the CV rooms at D34 and D37 (Table 6). There were more lying birds in the CV rooms than in the covered verandas at D34 and D37.

“CV vs. C, Indoor activity”: However, there was no significant difference between the inside of CV rooms and C rooms (Table 7).

“CV vs. C”: Broilers of the CV treatment expressed more walking and running behaviours than those of the C treatment at D34 and D37 (Table 8). There were more lying broilers counted in the

C treatment than the CV treatment at D37 but there was no significant difference between both treatments at D34.

Table 6. Mean (\pm standard deviation) of the standardized occurrence rates for walking and running behaviours and percentages of lying birds counted in covered verandas and indoor in CV rooms at D34 and D37.

	Age	Covered verandas	Indoor	Significance of effects (<i>p</i>)
Walking standardized occurrence rate	D34	73.9 (30.9)	18.3 (12.5)	<0.001
	D37	66.3 (26.9)	13.0 (12.1)	<0.001
Running standardized occurrence rate	D34	78.8 (53.9)	1.06 (2.15)	<0.001
	D37	96.8 (69.4)	0.62 (1.29)	<0.001
Percentage of lying broilers (%)	D34	77.6 (19.9)	97.28 (2.54)	<0.001
	D37	74.6 (15.5)	97.01 (4.41)	<0.001

Table 7. Mean (\pm standard deviation) of the standardized occurrence rates for walking and running behaviours and percentages of lying birds counted indoor in the CV and C rooms at D34 and D37.

	Age	CV rooms	C rooms	Significance of effects (<i>p</i>)
Walking standardized occurrence rate	D34	18.3 (12.5)	6.76 (4.03)	0.20
	D37	13.0 (12.1)	11.78 (6.62)	0.99
Running standardized occurrence rate	D34	1.06 (2.15)	0.81 (1.38)	1
	D37	0.62 (1.29)	0.43 (0.84)	1
Percentage of lying broilers (%)	D34	97.28 (2.54)	95.13 (5.43)	0.67
	D37	97.01 (4.41)	95.92 (3.68)	0.93

Table 8. Mean (\pm standard deviation) of the standardized occurrence rates for walking and running behaviours and percentages of lying birds counted in the C rooms and in average in the CV treatment at D34 and D37.

	Age	Average CV treatment	C rooms	Significance of effects (<i>p</i>)
Walking standardized occurrence rate	D34	47.16 (13.17)	6.76 (4.03)	<0.001
	D37	40.71 (18.45)	11.78 (6.62)	0.004
Running standardized occurrence rate	D34	40.07 (27.73)	0.81 (1.38)	0.05
	D37	48.89 (34.65)	0.43 (0.84)	0.01
Percentage of lying broilers (%)	D34	87.45 (9.88)	95.13 (5.43)	0.10
	D37	85.93 (9.24)	95.92 (3.68)	0.01

Covered veranda use

As the broilers aged, they were increasingly present in the covered verandas (regardless the hour of the day) ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 1, complementary data in Annex A1). However, the broilers significantly utilized the covered verandas less as the day progressed (regardless their age) ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 2 and Annex A2).

Figure 1. Mean number of broilers counted in 36 m² of covered verandas by day of age, all hour of the day from 8:00h (8 a.m.) to 20:00h (8 p.m.) considered (mean of three covered verandas)

Figure 2. Mean number of broilers counted in 36 m² of covered verandas by hour of the day, all day of the ages considered (mean of three covered verandas)

5 Discussion

The aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of the covered verandas on the health and welfare of broilers and on zootechnical indicators. The covered veranda access did not impact negatively (nor positively) the weights of the broilers nor their mortality during the rearing period. No consequence of the covered veranda access was found on feed and water consumptions, even though covered verandas stimulated the birds' activity.

As in previous studies (Weeks et al., 1994, Ruis et al., 2004, Bergmann et al., 2017), broilers in our study were more active outdoor, in the covered veranda, than inside the rooms, especially with more running behaviours but also with more walking behaviours. Broilers were observed more in lying position when in indoor than when in the covered verandas, but no difference was found when comparing indoor rooms of both treatments. However, overall, broilers in the CV treatment were observed less frequently in a lying position than those in the C treatment at 37 days of age. Additionally, broilers in the CV treatment exhibited more walking and running behaviours compared to those in the C treatment. Several hypotheses could be proposed to explain these results. First, the birds observed outdoors, in the covered verandas, may represent only the most active and healthy individuals in the flock, with the fewest leg problems, most prone to move further, leaving less active broilers inside. However, no broilers in either group exhibited gait issues. One possible explanation is that the greater available space in the covered veranda allowed the broilers to move more freely, resulting in more active behaviours observed, as high stocking densities may lead to restricted movement (EFSA, 2023). In our study, based on the observed number of broilers counted in half of the covered verandas, we estimate a maximum stocking density of 13.2 kg/m² in the entire covered veranda at the end of the rearing period, while the remaining stocking density inside the CV rooms was 22 kg/m². This difference in stocking density between the covered veranda and the room interior may have contributed to stimulating birds' activity in the covered verandas.

Nonetheless, lower density in covered veranda may not be the only possible contributor. Another explanation for the increased activity of the broilers in covered verandas could be the natural light and its intensity in outdoor conditions. Natural light may stimulate bird activity (Bailie et al., 2013, de Jong and Gunnink, 2019). However, natural light was also available inside the rooms through several windows. The rooms did though have lower light intensity compared to the outdoors. The intensity of natural light may play an even more significant role in birds' activity than the mere presence of natural light itself. In studies on artificial lights, birds tend to prefer dimmer light for inactive behaviours (e.g., resting) and brighter light for active behaviours such as preening, foraging or litter-directed active behaviours (Davis et al., 1999, Alvino et al., 2009, Deep et al., 2010). However, locomotor behaviours were not, or scarcely, impacted by artificial light intensity. Nevertheless, studies on environmental enrichments and natural light have shown an increased activity, including locomotor behaviours, in case of natural light in addition to enriched rearing conditions (Bailie et al., 2013, de Jong and Gunnink, 2019). If we consider the covered verandas as an enriched environment offering various sensory stimulations — such as fresh air, new odours, temperature variations, or direct sunlight — our results may align with those of Bailie et al. (2013) and de Jong and Gunnink (2019). This is particularly notable given that the indoor rearing environment was already enriched with elevated platforms, alfalfa bales, and natural light.

Thus, the higher activity level of broilers in the covered veranda, compared to indoor, may be explained by the lower stocking density, brighter natural light, and other outdoor sensory stimulations. Lastly, studies in other species, such as great apes (Kurtycz et al., 2014), have shown more positive affective states when given the choice between indoor and outdoor environments compared to when no choice was given. However, the present study lacks data to conclude on this hypothesis. Further research is needed to assess the affective states of broilers and other species given the option to move between indoor and outdoor environments, as there is a gap of knowledge on this topic.

The broilers in our study used the covered verandas more and more as they got older, as already shown in Bergmann's study (2017). Bergmann et al. hypothesized that cautiousness (predators' avoidance) played a role during the first days of covered veranda access, which was later replaced by possible habituation. Although opposite results (i.e., less covered veranda use by older birds) could have been anticipated and attributed to a general decrease in activity with age in broilers (Bizeray et al., 2002, Alvino et al., 2009), our study confirms Bergmann's findings with a different genetic strain. Nevertheless, the weather conditions may have play a role in the used of covered verandas in our study. Indeed, as shown by Bergmann et al. (2017), the higher the outside temperature, the more broilers are observed outside. However, the highest number of broilers counted outside in their study occurred at 37 days of age and temperatures around 1°C, suggesting that while both temperature and the age of the birds influence their use of covered verandas, age may have a greater impact. During our study, local temperatures, according to meteorological records, ranged from 1.2°C to 21.1°C. However, the temperature in the covered verandas was not recorded, preventing a correlation analysis between veranda use and temperature. Further studies should investigate the impact of weather conditions, seasonal variations, and their influence on broiler occupancy of covered verandas.

In the present study, the number of birds in the covered verandas was recorded throughout the day, at two-hour intervals from 08:00 to 20:00. More broilers were observed in the covered verandas in the early hours of the day compared to later, regardless of their age. This result may be linked to the daily activity rhythm of broilers. Broilers exhibit a biphasic activity pattern, with peaks in the morning and evening, which develops in young chicks and persists into adulthood (Bessei et al., 2023). This could explain the higher number of broilers in the covered verandas in the morning, where they were more active compared to when in the rooms. However, the expected evening peak in activity may not have been captured in our observations, if it occurred after 20:00, beyond the recording schedule and close to the sunset (at this season, the sunset occurred between 20:45 and 21:10). Indeed, as shown on figure 1, the number of broilers in the covered verandas started to increase again after 18:00.

Broilers with access to covered verandas exhibited fewer hock burns compared to those in the control group, while no broilers in either group showed signs of footpad dermatitis or gait issues. Both hock burns and footpad dermatitis are multifactorial conditions but are primarily associated with poor litter quality (EFSA, 2023). In this study, the litter quality indoor was good (mean score < 1) and did not differ between the treatments, ruling out litter condition as the cause of the

observed hock burns. Likewise, although not noted, the litter quality in the covered veranda was good (personal observation). According to Haslam et al. (2006), as the plantar surface of the foot is in contact with the litter both when the bird is active and resting, footpad dermatitis is more closely linked to litter quality than hock burns. Conversely, hock burns are more indicative of prolonged lying behaviour, which reflects inactivity. Thus, increased broiler activity reduces the risk of hock burns by minimizing the contact between the hocks and the litter (de Jong et al., 2016). This aligns with our findings, as broilers in the C group were more observed in a lying position at the end of the rearing period than those with access to covered verandas, and exhibited more hock burns.

Stocking density may also influence foot and hock lesions (Knierim, 2013, Mocz et al., 2022), but this effect occurs indirectly, mainly through factors such as degradation of the rearing environment - particularly litter quality (Dawkins et al., 2004, EFSA, 2023) - and restricted movement, which increases the time spent on suboptimal litter. In this study, stocking densities were relatively low. For the CV group, the final stocking density, considering both the indoor area and the covered veranda, was approximately 18.6 kg/m². For the C group, it reached 26 kg/m² at the end of the rearing period. Neither of the densities appeared to affect litter quality. The increased activity observed in broilers with access to covered verandas appears to be the main contributing factor to the reduction in hock burns observed in the CV treatment.

Although we cannot confirm that all broilers in the CV group utilized the covered verandas, the positive effects of access to a covered veranda remain visible. Furthermore, even if not all birds used the covered veranda area, it could still have indirect benefits. For instance, Ross (2006) demonstrated that providing access to a private space improved welfare in polar bears, even when it was rarely used, suggesting that the provision of choice was more impactful than the use of this private space itself. While Ross' study focused on a very different species and a small sample size, the principle of offering choice may, to some extent, be extrapolated to poultry and to the benefits of covered veranda access.

6 Conclusions

Giving access to a covered veranda brought welfare benefits such as better hock condition and more active behaviours. In addition, the covered veranda provided birds with the choice between staying indoors or moving to a completely different environment, which may influence other welfare indicators, such as their affective state or stress levels (not assessed). Nonetheless, no zootechnical indicators were impacted. While the construction of a covered veranda represents a substantial investment, this study suggests that such outdoor access could serve as an interesting complement or alternative to free-range systems. This topic deserves further research to better understand how the covered veranda access impacts the affective states of broilers, to determine the optimal age for granting access, to study the impact of seasonal variations on the use of covered verandas by the broilers, and to replicate this experimental protocol with other genetic strains to validate our findings.

7 References

- ALVINO, G. M., ARCHER, G. S. & MENCH, J. A. 2009. Behavioural time budgets of broiler chickens reared in varying light intensities. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 118, 54-61.
- BAILIE, C. L., BALL, M. E. & O'CONNELL, N. E. 2013. Influence of the provision of natural light and straw bales on activity levels and leg health in commercial broiler chickens. *Animal*, 7, 618-26.
- BERGMANN, S., LOUTON, H., WESTERMAIER, C., WILUTZKY, K., BENDER, A., BACHMEIER, J., ERHARD, M. H. & RAUCH, E. 2016. Field trial on animal-based measures for animal welfare in slow growing broilers reared under an alternative concept suitable for the German market. *Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift*, 453-461.
- BERGMANN, S., SCHWARZER, A., WILUTZKY, K., LOUTON, H., BACHMEIER, J., SCHMIDT, P., ERHARD, M. & RAUCH, E. 2017. Behavior as welfare indicator for the rearing of broilers in an enriched husbandry environment—A field study. *Journal of Veterinary Behavior: Clinical Applications and Research*, 19, 90-101.
- BESSEI, W., TETENS, J., BENNEWITZ, J., FALKER-GIESKE, C., HOFMANN, T. & PIEPHO, H. P. 2023. Disturbed circadian rhythm of locomotor activity of pullets is related to feather pecking in laying hens. *Poult Sci*, 102, 102548.
- BIZERAY, D., ESTEVEZ, I., LETERRIER, C. & FAURE, J. M. 2002. Effects of increasing environmental complexity on the physical activity of broiler chickens. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 79, 27-41.
- DAVIS, N. J., PRESCOTT, N. B., SAVORY, C. J. & WATHES, C. M. 1999. Preferences of growing fowls for different light intensities in relation to age, strain and behaviour. *Animal Welfare*, 8, 193-203.
- DAWKINS, M. S., COOK, P. A., WHITTINGHAM, M. J., MANSELL, K. A. & HARPER, A. E. 2003. What makes free-range broiler chickens range? In situ measurement of habitat preference. *Animal Behaviour*, 66, 151-160.
- DAWKINS, M. S., DONNELLY, C. A. & JONES, T. A. 2004. Chicken welfare is influenced more by housing conditions than by stocking density. *Nature*, 427, 342-344.
- DE JONG, I. C. & GUNNINK, H. 2019. Effects of a commercial broiler enrichment programme with or without natural light on behaviour and other welfare indicators. *Animal*, 13, 384-391.
- DE JONG, I. C., HINDLE, V. A., BUTTERWORTH, A., ENGEL, B., FERRARI, P., GUNNINK, H., PEREZ MOYA, T., TUYTTENS, F. A. & VAN REENEN, C. G. 2016. Simplifying the Welfare Quality(R) assessment protocol for broiler chicken welfare. *Animal*, 10, 117-27.
- DEEP, A., SCHWEAN-LARDNER, K., CROWE, T. G., FANCHER, B. I. & CLASSEN, H. L. 2010. Effect of light intensity on broiler production, processing characteristics, and welfare. *Poultry Science*, 89, 2326-2333.
- EFSA 2023. Scientific Opinion on the welfare of broilers on farm. *EFSA Journal*, 21, 236.
- EL-DEEK, A. & EL-SABROUT, K. 2019. Behaviour and meat quality of chicken under different housing systems. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 75, 105-114.
- ENGLUND, M. D. & CRONIN, K. A. 2023. Choice, control, and animal welfare: definitions and essential inquiries to advance animal welfare science. *Front Vet Sci*, 10, 1250251.
- GOCSIK, É., BROOSHOOFT, S. D., DE JONG, I. C. & SAATKAMP, H. W. 2016. Cost-efficiency of animal welfare in broiler production systems: A pilot study using the Welfare Quality® assessment protocol. *Agricultural Systems*, 146, 55-69.

- GORANSSON, L., GUNNARSSON, S., WALLENBECK, A. & YNGVESSON, J. 2021. Behaviour in Slower-Growing Broilers and Free-Range Access on Organic Farms in Sweden. *Animals (Basel)*, 11.
- GUINEBRETIERE, M., WARIN, L., MOYSAN, J.-P., MÉDA, B., MOCZ, F., LE BIHAN-DUVAL, E., THOMAS, R., KEITA, A. & MIGNON-GRASTEAU, S. 2024. Effects of strain and stocking density on leg health, activity, and use of enrichments in conventional broiler chicken production. *Poultry Science*, 103:103993.
- HASLAM, S. M., KNOWLES, T. G., BROWN, S. N., WILKINS, L. J., KESTIN, S. C., WARRISS, P. D. & NICOL, C. J. 2006. Factors affecting the prevalence of foot pad dermatitis, hock burn and breast burn in broiler chicken. *British Poultry Science*, 48, 264-275.
- KNIERIM, U. 2013. Effects of stocking density on the behaviour and bodily state of broilers fattened with a target liveweight of 2 kg. *Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift*, 126, 149-155.
- KURTYCZ, L. M., WAGNER, K. E. & ROSS, S. R. 2014. The choice to access outdoor areas affects the behavior of great apes. *J Appl Anim Welf Sci*, 17, 185-97.
- LOURENCO DA SILVA, M. I., ALMEIDA PAZ, I. C. L., CHAVES, G. H. C., ALMEIDA, I. C. L., OUROS, C. C. D., SOUZA, S. R. L., MILBRADT, E. L., CALDARA, F. R., SATIN, A. J. G., COSTA, G. A. D. & GLAVINA, A. S. G. 2021. Behaviour and animal welfare indicators of broiler chickens housed in an enriched environment. *PLoS One*, 16, e0256963.
- LOUTON, H., KEPPLER, C., ERHARD, M., VAN TUIJL, O., BACHMEIER, J., DAMME, K., REESE, S. & RAUCH, E. 2019. Animal-based welfare indicators of 4 slow-growing broiler genotypes for the approval in an animal welfare label program. *Poultry Science*, 98, 2326-2337.
- MOCZ, F., MICHEL, V., JANVROT, M., MOYSAN, J. P., KEITA, A., RIBER, A. B. & GUINEBRETIERE, M. 2022. Positive Effects of Elevated Platforms and Straw Bales on the Welfare of Fast-Growing Broiler Chickens Reared at Two Different Stocking Densities. *Animals (Basel)*, 12.
- ROSS, S. R. 2006. Issues of choice and control in the behaviour of a pair of captive polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*). *Behav Processes*, 73, 117-20.
- RUIS, M. A. W., COENEN, E., VAN HARN, J., LENSSENS, P. & RODENBURG, T. B. 2004. Effect of an outdoor run and natural light on welfare of fast growing broilers. *In: Proceedings of the 38th ISAE Congress, Helsinki, Finland, August 3-7, 2004, p.255.*
- WEEKS, C. A., NICOL, C. J., SHERWIN, C. M. & KESTIN, S. C. 1994. Comparison of the Behaviour of Broiler Chickens in Indoor and Free-Range Environments. *Animal Welfare*, 3, 179-192.
- WELFARE QUALITY® 2009. Welfare Quality® assessment protocol for poultry (broilers, laying hens). *Welfare Quality® Consortium, Lelystad, Netherlands.*

8 Annex 1

Figure A1. Mean number of broilers in 36 m² of covered verandas by age at each hour of the day from 8:00h (8 a.m.) to 20:00h (8 p.m.) (mean of three covered verandas and associated standard deviation)

Figure A2. Mean number of broilers in 36 m² of covered verandas by hour of the day each day of age from D22 to slaughter (mean of three covered verandas and associated standard deviation)

About EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is one of the four European Union Reference Centres for Animal Welfare. It focuses on poultry and other small farmed animals welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from hatch/birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's main objective is to scientifically and technically support the European Commission and Member States for implementation of welfare legislation. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens;
- Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

Partners

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following four partner institutions:

- ANSES, France
- IRTA, Spain
- ANIVET, AU, Denmark
- IZSLER, Italy

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the EURCAW only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Activities of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Good Practices
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics, identify research needs and perform scientific and technical studies to fill the gaps of knowledge;
- Training
Reviewing existing training activities and developing new training materials, webinars and knowledge pills for official inspectors and competent authorities;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, and newsletter.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of poultry and other small farmed animals' welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of poultry and other small farmed animals welfare in the EU. For more information go to the Q2E webform available online [here](https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw>. All Q2E answers are available.